

THE CONDENSATION OF ALDEHYDES WITH β -KETO-ESTERS.
PART III. 3-HYDROXY-, 4-HYDROXY- AND
3:4-DIHYDROXY-BENZALDEHYDES

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3-Hydroxy-, 4-hydroxy- and 3:4-dihydroxy-benzaldehydes have been condensed with ethyl acetoacetate and ethyl benzoylacetate in the presence of piperidine, pyridine and lutidine. The resulting *mono*- and *bis*-esters have been characterised.

In Parts I and II of this series (Pandya and Miss Pandya Jr., *Agra Univ. J. Res.*, 1955, 4, 305, 345) salicylaldehyde and nine of its derived aldehydes (including resorcyraldehyde) have been condensed with ethyl acetoacetate and ethyl benzoylacetate in the presence of piperidine, pyridine and 2:6-lutidine to obtain the corresponding coumarins. In the present paper this work has been extended to 3-hydroxy-, 4-hydroxy- and 3:4-dihydroxy-benzaldehydes. While condensations with ethyl acetoacetate have yielded two types of products, viz., (1) *mono*-esters (I) (substituted cinnamic esters) and (2) *bis*-esters (II), (substituted glutaric esters), depending on the quantity of the keto-ester used, only the *mono*-esters have been obtained in condensations with ethyl benzoylacetate.

The *bis*-esters from ethyl acetoacetate undergo ring-chain tautomerism (IIA) as well as keto-enol tautomerism (IIB). The cyclic tautomer itself affords other keto-enol tautomers in cyclic form. Though all these different open-chain and cyclic tautomers are not separable here, yet their presence is evident from the different open-chain and cyclic products obtained by hydrolysis. Also Knoevenagel (*Ber.*, 1896, 29, 172) recorded one illustration of ethyl benzylidene-*bis*-acetoacetate, where out of the twelve possible tautomers (8 keto and 4 enol), six (3 keto and 3 enol) were separated by him and other workers.

While the *mono*-esters from monohydroxybenzaldehydes had yielded the corresponding acids (III) on hydrolysis with 5-10% NaOH solution, those from dihydroxybenzaldehydes yielded only resins. The three β -(*mono*- or dihydroxyphenyl)-glutaric acids (IV) are obtained from the three *bis*-esters (II) even by mild alkali hydrolysis. Formation of these acids confirms the open-chain configuration of the *bis*-esters.

On treatment with phosphoric acid (cf. Horning and Field, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 384) the three *bis*-esters (II) gave the respective *cyclo*keto-di-esters (V), which were, however, not further hydrolysed to the cyclic ketones (cf. Knoevenagel, *loc. cit.*). Formation of these ketones confirms the cyclic configuration of the *bis*-esters.

The *mono*-esters (I) from both the keto-esters react with hydroxylamine to afford the corresponding *isoxazolones* (VI). The *bis*-esters (IIA, IIB) react with one mole of 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine to furnish the corresponding derivative.

CHART I

Mono-esters :
Substituted cinnamic esters.

Bis-esters :
Substituted glutaric esters.

Substituted cinnamic acids.

Substituted glutaric acids.

cycloKeto-di-esters.

Isoxazolones

where

R is, a = 3-OH.C₆H₄, b = 4-OH.C₆H₄, c = 3:4-(OH)₂.C₆H₃,
R₁ = Me
R₂ = Ph

TABLE I

3-Hydroxybenzaldehyde : Condensations.

No.	Base.	Molar proportions.	Temp.	Time.	Ester.	Yield.	With ethyl acetoacetate.			
							Temp.	Time.	Ester.	Yield.
1.	Piperidine	1 : 1 : 0.1	20°	10 hrs.	Mono	86%	30°	20 hrs.	Mono	92%
2.	"	1 : 2 : 0.1	20°	6	Bis	98	30°	24	"	84
3.	Pyridine	1 : 1 : 6	Water-bath	24	Mono	56	Water-bath	16	"	62
4.	"	1 : 2 : 6	"	24	"	48	"	16	"	56
5.	Lutidine	1 : 1 : 3	"	10	"	68	"	8	"	74
6.	"	1 : 2 : 3	"	10	"	52	"	8	"	64

TABLE II

Products from 3-hydroxybenzaldehyde.

Products.	No.	M.P.	Cryst. shape.	Mol. formula.	Analysis (%).	
					Found.	Calc.
1. *Ethyl (3-hydroxybenzylidene)- <i>mono</i> -acetoacetate	I:R _{1a}	140°	White plates	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₄	C : 66.76 H : 6.00	65.66 5.98
2. Ethyl (3-hydroxybenzylidene)- <i>mono</i> -benzoylacetate	I:R _{2a}	156°	White cubes	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₄	C : 72.90 H : 5.40	72.97 5.46
3. Ethyl (3-hydroxybenzylidene)- <i>bis</i> -acetoacetate	II:a	170°	White tiny needles	C ₁₉ H ₂₄ O ₇	C : 62.42 H : 6.58	62.63 6.59
4. 3-Hydroxybenzylidene- <i>mono</i> -acetoacetic acid	III:R _{1a}	118°	Yellow needles	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₄	C : 63.87 H : 4.9	64.07 4.8
5. 3-Hydroxybenzylidene- <i>mono</i> -benzoylacetic acid	III:R _{2a}	134°	White needles	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₄	C : 71.20 H : 4.25	71.6 4.5
6. β -(3-Hydroxyphenyl)-glutaric acid	IVa	188° (eff)	White needles	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₅	C : 54.46 H : 5.3	54.4 5.3
7. 1-Methyl-3-(3-hydroxyphenyl)-2 : 4-dicarbethoxy-6-cyclohexene-5-one	Va	80°	White prisms	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ O ₅	C : 66.36 H : 6.86	66.04 6.36
8. 3-Methyl-4-(3-hydroxybenzylidene)- <i>isoxazolone</i> -5	VI:R _{1a}	220° (decomp.)	Yellow cubes	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₃ N	N : 7.0	6.9
9. 3-Phenyl-4-(3-hydroxybenzylidene)- <i>isoxazolone</i> -5	VI:R _{2a}	197° (decomp.)	Pale yellow needles	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₃ N	N : 5.4	5.28
10. 2 : 4-Dinitrophenyl-hydrazone.	From IIa	224° (decomp.)	Brick-red needles	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ O ₁₀ N ₄	N : 10.16	10.29

*Also prepared by Gupta & Dutt (M.Sc. Theses, Agra Univ, 1946-47, unpublished).

TABLE III

4-Hydroxybenzaldehyde: Condensations.

No.	Base.	Molar proportions.	Temp.	Time.	Ester product.	Yield.
With ethyl acetoacetate.						
1.	Piperidine	1:1:0.1	28°	3 hrs.	Mono	96%
2.	"	1:2:0.2	18°	72	Bis	86
3.	"	1:1:0.1	18°	28	"	93
4.	Pyridine	1:1:6	Water-bath	16	Mono	59
5.	"	1:2:6	"	16	"	40
6.	"	1:3:6	"	16	Bis	40
7.	Lutidine	1:1:1	"	6	Mono	26
8.	"	1:1:3	"	6	"	86
9.	"	1:2:3	"	8	"	51
With ethyl benzoylacetate.						
1.	Piperidine	1:1:0.1	30°	10	Mono	98
2.	"	1:2:0.1	30°	12	"	95
3.	Pyridine	1:1:6	Water-bath	16	"	66
4.	"	1:2:6	"	16	"	48
5.	Lutidine	1:1:3	"	8	"	88
6.	"	1:2:3	"	8	"	52

TABLE IV

Products from 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde.

Products.	No.	M.P.	Cryst. shape.	Mol. formula.	Analysis (%).	
					Found.	Calc.
1. *Ethyl (4-hydroxybenzylidene)-mono-acetoacetate	I:R ₁ b	140°	Yellow plates	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₄	C: 67.03 H: 5.98	66.66 5.98
2. Ethyl (4-hydroxybenzylidene)-mono-benzoylacetate	I:R ₂ b	180°	White cubes	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₄	C: 72.6 H: 5.2	72.07 5.46
3. Ethyl (4-hydroxybenzylidene)-bis-acetoacetate	IIb	175°	White needles	C ₁₉ H ₂₄ O ₇	C: 62.53 H: 6.54	62.63 6.59
4. 4-Hydroxybenzylidene-mono-acetoacetic acid	III:R ₁ b	121°	Yellow needles	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₄	C: 64.2 H: 4.8	64.07 4.8
5. 4-Hydroxybenzylidene-mono-benzoylacetic acid	III:R ₂ b	154°	White needles	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₄	C: 72.4 H: 4.6	71.6 4.5
6. β-(4-Hydroxyphenyl)-glutaric acid	IVb	210° (eff.)	"	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₅	C: 54.26 H: 5.6	54.4 5.3
7. 1-Methyl-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-2:4-dicarbethoxy-6-cyclohexene-5-one	Vb	98°	White prisms	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O ₆	C: 65.58 H: 6.3	66.04 6.36
8. 3-Methyl-4-(4-hydroxybenzylidene)-isoxazolone-5	VI:R ₁ b	215° (decomp.)	Yellow cubes	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₃ N	N: 6.68	6.9
9. 3-Phenyl-4-(4-hydroxybenzylidene)-isoxazolone-5	VI:R ₂ b	206° (decomp.)	Pale yellow needles	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ O ₃ N	N: 5.16	5.28
10. 2:4-Dinitrophenyl-hydrazone	From IIb	219° (decomp.)	Shining red needles	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ O ₁₀ N ₄	N: 10.34	10.29

* Also prepared by Gupta & Dutt⁶ (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE V

3 : 4-Dihydroxybenzaldehyde : Condensations.

No.	Base.	Molar proportions.	Temp.	Time.	Ester product.	Yield.
With ethyl acetoacetate.						
1.	Piperidine	1 : 1 : 0.1	18°	26 hrs.	Mono	80%
2.	"	1 : 2 : 0.1	18°	20	Bis	83
3.	Pyridine	1 : 1 : 6	Water-bath	12	Resin	...
4.	"	1 : 2 : 6	"	12	"	...
5.	"	1 : 1 : 3	20-22°	3 weeks	Bis	24
6.	Lutidine	1 : 1 : 3	Water-bath	12-43 hrs.	Resin	...
		or	or			
		1 : 2 : 3	60-70°			
7.	"	1 : 1 : 3	20-22°	3 weeks	Bis	32.6
With ethyl benzoylacetate.						
1.	Piperidine	1 : 1 : 0.1	28°	24 hrs.	Mono	72
2.	"	1 : 2 : 0.1	28°	24	"	89
3.	Pyridine	1 : 1 : 6	Water-bath	12-24	Resin	...
	"	1 : 2 : 6	"	12-24	...	...
4.	"	1 : 1 : 3	26-28°	6 weeks	Mono	56
5.	Lutidine	1 : 1 : 3	Water-bath	5-24 hrs.	Resin	...
	"	1 : 2 : 3	"	5-24	...	...
6.	"	1 : 1 : 1.5	26-28°	6 weeks	Mono	69

TABLE VI

Products from 3 : 4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde.

Products.	No.	M.P.	Cryst. shape.	Mol. formula.	Analysis (%).	
					Found.	Calc.
1. Ethyl (3 : 4-dihydroxybenzylidene)-mono-acetoacetate	I : R ₁ C	130°	Brown needles	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₅	C : 62.58 H : 5.40	62.4 5.6
2. Ethyl (3 : 4-dihydroxybenzylidene)-mono-benzoylacetate	1 : R ₂ C	172°	Brown cubes	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₃	C : 69.5 H : 5.6	69.23 5.12
3. Ethyl (3 : 4-dihydroxybenzylidene)-bis-acetoacetate	IIc	163°	Green thin needles	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ O ₈	C : 60.12 H : 6.99	60.0 6.7
4. β -(3 : 4-dihydroxyphenyl)-glutaric acid	IVc	195° eff.	White needles	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₆	C : 55.22 H : 4.98	55.0 5.0
5. 1-Methyl-3-(3 : 4-dihydroxyphenyl)-2 : 4-dicarbethoxy-6-cyclohexene-5-one	Vc	107°	Brown plates	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ O ₇	C : 62.66 H : 5.96	62.98 6.07
6. 3-Methyl-4-(3 : 4-dihydroxybenzylidene)-isoxazolone-5	VI : R ₁ C	202°	Yellow cubes	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₄ N	N : 6.12	6.3
7. 3-Phenyl-4-(3 : 4-dihydroxybenzylidene)-isoxazolone-5	VI : R ₂ C	204°	Pale yellow needles	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₄ N	N : 5.24	4.99

From the data (Tables I-VI), it is generally seen that (i) the reactivity of mono hydroxybenzaldehydes is greater than that of the dihydroxybenzaldehydes, (ii) the reaction is slower but the yields are better with ethyl benzoylacetate than with ethyl acetoacetate and (iii) the reactivity of the bases is in the order: piperidine >lutidine >pyridine.

EXPERIMENTAL

The general procedure was, as before (Parts I and II, *loc. cit.*), to dissolve the aldehyde and the ester (1:1 or 1:2 moles) in a minimum quantity of cold or hot absolute alcohol, and to add to it an alcoholic solution of piperidine (0.1 mole., 3.8 by volume). The contents were kept at room temperature till complete solidification occurred. With pyridine or lutidine, the method was to mix the two reactants and the base in 1:1:6 or 3, or 1:2:6 molar proportions, and to heat them on a water-bath for 5 to 10 hours, or even longer, till a drop of the reaction mixture gave a precipitate or a turbidity with dilute HCl. In the case of 3:4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde, heating with tertiary bases gave a resinous mass; these condensations were therefore carried out at room temperature without any solvent. Solidification took place in 3 to 6 weeks (Table V). After completion, the reaction product, if solid, was filtered and washed with dilute alcohol (40%). The filtrate usually provided more product on adding water. Where solidification did not occur, the liquid reaction mixtures were acidified with HCl (dil.) and the products were thus precipitated out, leaving the excess of base in solution. Recrystallisation in all cases was done from absolute alcohol or from glacial acetic acid, both furnishing pure products, but glacial acetic acid afforded colorless (white) crystals, while alcohol left a slightly yellow colour behind.

For the distinction between the mono-(I) and the bis-(II) esters, the general tests were as detailed below.

Baeyer's reagent (alkaline KMnO_4) was decolorised at once (within one second) in the case of the mono-ester, while decolorisation took place very slowly (from 30 to 100 seconds) in case of the bis-ester. The mono-ester also decolorised bromine water in cold, but the bis-ester did not. Tetranitromethane developed a very pale yellow colour with the saturated bis-esters and a very deep yellow colour with the unsaturated mono-esters. The benzoyl-acetic esters showed a deep red colour with cold H_2SO_4 (conc.) which on warming turned yellow, if *mono*, and brown, if *bis*. The melting points of the bis-esters were always higher than those of the mono-esters. Both the esters were soluble in alcohol, acetone and ether, and insoluble in benzene, chloroform and carbon tetrachloride; but while the mono-ester was soluble in hot water and insoluble in cold water and in cold or hot glacial acetic acid, the bis-ester was insoluble in hot water and soluble in hot glacial acetic acid.

Hydrolysis.— α -Acetyl- or α -benzoyl-mono-hydroxycinnamic acids (III) were prepared from the mono-esters (I) by hydrolysis with a 5% solution of NaOH. Usually mixing 1 g. of the ester and 10 c.c. of 5% alkali and leaving overnight afforded on neutralisation the required acid. In some cases the ester had to be dissolved at start in warm alkali. All these acids decolorised Baeyer's reagent.

β -(Mono- or dihydroxyphenyl)-glutaric acids (IV) were obtained from the bis-esters (II) of the acetoacetic ester by alkaline hydrolysis. The ester and 40% KOH were mixed and were refluxed directly for 4 to 6 hours.

The three *cyclo*keto-di-esters (V) were also obtained from the bis-products (II) of acetoacetic ester. The bis-product (2.3 g.) was refluxed with a mixture of glacial acetic acid (4 c.c.), acetic anhydride (0.6 c.c.) and phosphoric acid (85%, 0.5 c.c.) on a low flame for 2 to 3 hours. The cooled contents were added to 50 c.c. of water and the oily product was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was first neutralised with Na_2CO_3 , and was washed successively with 5% NaOH, 5% acetic acid and water. The ether was evaporated and the residue was recrystallised from absolute alcohol.

The 3-methyl- or 3-phenyl-4-(mono or dihydroxy-benzylidene)-isoxazolones-5 (VI) were prepared from all the six mono-esters (I). The mono-ester and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1:1 mole) were dissolved together in a little absolute alcohol, a few drops of NaOH (5%) were added and the mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 1 hour. The crystals of (VI) separated out on cooling or on leaving overnight in ice.

The two bis-esters (II) from the two monohydroxybenzaldehydes gave red needles of the corresponding 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones in a few minutes on a water-bath.

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